

Multi objective optimization for the optimal scheduling of a Battery Swapping Station integrated with photovoltaic

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ABSTRACT

Battery Swapping Stations (BSS) offer a faster alternative to conventional EV charging, by replacing depleted batteries with fully charged ones. This decoupling of charging and discharging phases significantly reduces waiting times. However, managing these operations, especially when integrated with renewable energy sources like solar power, requires complex optimization. This paper presents a novel mixed-integer linear programming algorithm to optimize the operations of a BSS integrated with a photovoltaic power plant. The algorithm simulates yearly operations, considering hourly energy prices and grid constraints. It aims to maximize station revenue by optimally scheduling battery charging after swaps and utilizing renewable energy. Simulation results demonstrate significant economic savings, highlighting the algorithm's effectiveness in capitalizing on cost differentials in electricity pricing. This approach provides valuable insights for enhancing the economic viability and operational efficiency of BSS integrated with renewable energy sources.

KEYWORDS

Electric Vehicles (EVs), Battery Swapping, Energy Services, Optimization Models, Renewable Energy, Feasibility Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The release of greenhouse gases (GHGs) into the atmosphere is a significant driver of global warming [1]. The transportation sector, heavily reliant on fossil fuels, is a major contributor to global emissions, with an average annual growth rate of 1.7% [2]. Road transportation, consuming approximately 2000 Mtoe annually, accounts for nearly 50% of total oil consumption across all sectors. Over the past five decades, road transportation's oil demand has nearly tripled, raising sustainability concerns [3]. Electrification, particularly through the adoption of battery electric vehicles (BEVs), is crucial for decarbonizing transportation. BEVs produce zero tailpipe emissions, and their lifecycle emissions will continue to decrease as renewable energy sources (RES) play a larger role in power generation [4]. Achieving the goal of limiting the global temperature rise to 1.5°C requires EVs to account for 60% of total vehicle sales by 2030 [5]. The integration of EVs into the transportation sector offers numerous benefits beyond reducing GHG emissions. Electric power as a transportation fuel eliminates tailpipe emissions, can be sourced from renewable and non-emitting energy generation, and offers lower operating costs [6]. EVs utilize existing electric grid infrastructure for recharging, facilitating adoption. Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology allows EVs to serve as mobile energy storage units, enabling energy to flow back to the grid during peak demand periods. This technology contributes to load balancing, voltage regulation, and frequency stabilization [7]. Aligning EV charging with periods of high renewable energy

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availability reduces curtailment and enhances grid sustainability [8]. Socioeconomic benefits include enhanced national energy security by reducing reliance on imported fossil fuels, noise reduction, improved air quality in cities, and lower overall transportation costs [9]. Despite these advantages, challenges hinder EV adoption. Increased charging demand can strain the electricity grid, necessitating infrastructure upgrades [10 – 11]. The high upfront cost of EVs remains a barrier, while extended wait times at charging stations and limited charging options discourage adoption. Battery swapping emerges as an innovative solution, allowing EVs to quickly replace depleted batteries with fully charged ones, reducing wait times and alleviating range anxiety [12]. Battery Swapping Stations (BSSs) provide fully charged batteries in under five minutes and mitigate renewable energy curtailments by integrating variable renewable energy into grids [13]. A key advantage of battery swapping is the use of batteries housed at swapping stations for offering energy services [14]. While research on energy storage systems often focuses on frequency regulation and grid applications [15], BSS energy services can be classified into three categories: ISO/RTO services for Independent System Operators [16]; utility services for grid operators, including voltage regulation and battery storage integration [17]; and customer services for enterprises, such as demand charge reduction and increased photovoltaic (PV) self-consumption. To effectively deliver these services, BSS operations must be optimally managed and integrated into smart grids. This requires accounting for variables like EV arrivals, energy needs, supply and demand dynamics, and power system behaviour. Advanced optimization methods are critical for achieving optimal outcomes [18]. This paper presents a case study of a Charging Point Operator (CPO) in northern Italy planning a BSS installation with a photovoltaic power plant adjacent to an existing charging point. While adding to the system’s load, the BSS introduces flexibility in battery energy management, enabling load-shifting optimization to enhance efficiency and integration.

RESEARCH AND METHODS

Problem definition: optimization problem

The paper describes an optimization problem related to a BSS application. An optimization problem comprises three main elements: an objective function, a set of decision variables, and a set of constraints that limit the values assignable to the decision variables. The optimization algorithm determines the optimal value of the objective function by assigning values to the decision variables while adhering to the constraints. In this case, a MILP algorithm has been implemented using the Spider programming environment in Python and the PuLP library [19]. MILP algorithms, while requiring more computational resources than heuristic methods, offer the advantage of being based on robust solvers and mathematical foundations, ensuring the certainty of the solution with a known optimality level. The GLPK solver was used to find the optimal solution [20].

Objective function. the objective function of the problem is constituted by the sum of the costs related with the energy and the power demand.

$$O.F. = \min \left\{ P_p \cdot F_p + \sum_{i:1}^N \left[E_g(i) \cdot (F_e(i) + F_{ge}(i)) - PV_{inj}(i) \cdot F_{inj}(i) \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

Where i is the timestep, P_p [kW] the peak power demand during the billing period, F_p [€/kW] the peak power fee, $E_g(i)$ [kWh] the energy withdrawn from the grid at timestep i , $F_e(i)$ [€/kWh] the price of energy withdrawn from the grid, $F_{ge}(i)$ [€/kWh] the grid fee for withdrawn energy, $PV_{inj}(i)$ [kWh] the energy injected into the grid at timestep i and $F_{inj}(i)$ [€/kWh] the price of energy injected into the grid. The objective function consists thus of two

main components. The first is the power cost, which refers to the cost associated with the maximum contracted power that can be supplied by the electrical grid. The second component is the energy cost, which is the cost related to the energy drawn from or injected into the grid during each time step. This cost is calculated by multiplying the energy by its price.

Problem constraints. In optimization problems, constraints establish boundary conditions for the variables influencing the objective function. In Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problems, these constraints must be linear equalities or inequalities. For this optimization problem, constraints include energy balance and battery operations. The energy balance constraint ensures that grid and photovoltaic supply, and battery charging/discharging match energy demand at each time step. Battery constraints limit charge/discharge power and enforce state of charge (SOC) limits to protect battery lifetime.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (E_g(i) + PV_l(i)) = \sum_{i=1}^N (E_d(i) + (B_{ch}(i) - B_{dh}(i))) \quad (2)$$

Eq. 2 is an energy balance constraint that ensures the total energy supplied and stored matches the demand for each time period. It states that the sum of electricity drawn from the grid ($E_g(i)$) and energy produced by the PV power plant ($PV_l(i)$) must equal the total energy demand ($E_d(i)$) plus the net energy used for battery charging ($B_{ch}(i) - B_{dh}(i)$), accounting for charge-discharge efficiency losses.

$$0 \leq P_{B_{ch}}(i) \leq P_{grid}(i) \quad (3)$$

$$0 \leq P_{B_{dh}}(i) \leq P_{B_{MAX}} \quad (4)$$

$$0 \leq B_{SOC}(i) \leq B_C \quad (5)$$

$$B_{SOC}(i) = B_{SOC}(i-1) + B_{ch}(i) - B_{dh}(i) \quad (6)$$

$$B_{dh}(i) = B_{SWAP}(i) \quad (7)$$

$$PV(i) = PV_l(i) + PV_{inj}(i) \quad (8)$$

Eq. 3 limits the battery charging power ($P_{B_{ch}}$) to not exceed the power delivered by the grid (P_{grid}). Eq. 4 limits the battery discharging power ($P_{B_{dh}}$). Eq. 5 ensures the state of charge of the battery (B_{SOC}) remains within the allowable range, preventing overcharging and over-discharging. Eq. 6 describes how SOC changes with charging and discharging at each time step. Eq. 7 states that a swap order results in a fully charged battery being exchanged with a drained one, decreasing the overall SOC of the battery stack. Eq. 8 is the energy balance constraint over the total PV production that must equal the sum of the PV energy delivered to the load (PV_l) and to the grid (PV_{inj}).

Optimization variables. The optimization variables determine the final value of the objective function, and their value is computed by the algorithm to minimize the latter. In this case, the optimization variables are P_p , E_g , B_{ch} , PV_{inj} and PV_l .

Case study

The model was applied to a test case for a Charging Point Operator (CPO) planning to install a new charging station and a 500 kWp Photovoltaic power plant near an existing Battery Swapping Station (BSS). The new station will have 4 High-Power chargers (100 kW each). The BSS can support up to 21 battery slots, perform swaps in under 5 minutes, and charge over 10 batteries per hour. It has a 600-kW grid connection capacity to meet the maximum power demand, focusing on 50 daily swaps. The system model is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: System model

Charging point operator (CPO). Figure 2 shows the daily energy demand pattern at the charging station under typical conditions, with multiple vehicles using some or all available charging points simultaneously. The mean and maximum values of the power demand are shown for each quarter hour of the day. The mean values indicate low power demand during nighttime hours (1 AM to 6 AM), which increases in the early morning and peaks after 9 AM. The highest demand occurs between 12 PM and 3 PM, with up to four charging sessions active at once. The maximum values curve shows that power demand is influenced by the number of vehicles charging simultaneously and the maximum allowable charging power per vehicle, rarely reaching the upper limit of 400 kW.

Battery swapping station (CPO). The BSS model that has been chosen can support up to 21 battery slots and can perform a swap in less than 5 minutes, which could require charging more than 10 batteries per hour. Consequently, these installations can be equipped with a 600-kW grid connection capacity. Figure 3 shows the maximum and average daily power demand for the BSS. The literature has been reviewed to identify peak times when battery swaps are most likely to occur. A typical daily swap pattern shows low activity in the morning, swaps begin around 7 AM, with minimal or no activity at night due to station closures or low demand, increasing before noon, peaking in the afternoon, then gradually decreasing until a second peak around 9-10 PM as illustrated in Figure 4. In terms of power demand, without smart charging implementation, power usage is assumed to follow the swapping pattern, as batteries are charged after each swap to meet ongoing demand. Energy requirements for 50 daily swaps range from 2500 to 2800 kWh, averaging around 55 kWh per swap. This is based

on a typical 100 kWh battery, such as that of a fully electric SUV [21], with the battery's State of Charge (SOC) ideally maintained between 20% and 80% to maximize battery longevity.

Figure 2: Mean and maximum values for charging station power demand (Each Quarter Hour)

Figure 3: Maximum and average daily power demand for the BSS and the charging station

Figure 4: Battery swaps per hour

Photovoltaic system. The photovoltaic (PV) system was modelled according to [22], using a poly-crystalline module with a net cell opening area (A_{eff}) of 1.82 m², an efficiency of 14.6% in Standard Test Conditions (STC) and a peak power of 410 W [23]. The DC power delivered by the PV system was computed using Eq. 9, where G is the solar radiation and η_c is the cell efficiency, assumed to be equal to the STC efficiency for a simplified model. To calculate the effective AC power produced by the PV system, Balance of System (BOS) losses, which typically reduce DC power by 15%, must be considered. These losses are accounted for in the computation of AC power using Eq. 10, with a BOS efficiency (η_{BOS}) assumed to be 85%. Figure 5 depicts the energy PV production.

$$P_{PV}(DC) = \eta_c A_{eff} G \quad (9)$$

$$P_{PV}(AC) = P_{PV}(DC) \eta_{BOS} \quad (10)$$

Figure 5: PV production

RESULTS AND COMMENTS

The model was applied to a test case for a potential Charging Point Operator (CPO) in northern Italy, aiming to expand its business by installing a new Battery Swapping Station (BSS) near the existing charging station. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the charging station scenario, while Table 2 details the BSS scenario.

Table 1: Charging station - case study scenario

Daily charging sessions	Charging points	Installed power [kW]	Peak demand [kW]	Annual energy demand [kWh]
60	4	400	403	634,386.00

Table 3 lists the energy, grid, and management fees that users must pay in Italy. These fees include a variable energy fee based on the amount of withdrawn energy, a fixed power fee based on the maximum contracted power, and a fixed management fee covering all technical

and commercial management charges. The grid and management fees are set by the Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy Networks and Environments [24], while the energy fee is linked to the PUN or UNP (Unique National Price), the wholesale reference price of electricity on the Italian Power Exchange (IPEX) market [25]. The UNP is an hourly value; this paper considers the hourly average value of the UNP for 2024.

Table 2: BSS - case study scenario

Battery Slots	Max Swaps per Hour	Installed power [kW]	Peak demand [kW]	Annual energy demand [kWh]
50	10	600	376	826.588

Assuming that installing a Battery Swapping Station (BSS) alongside the charging station can balance the load, improve power utilization, and reduce peak capacity requirements, the combined demand of the charging station and BSS has been used as the load profile for optimization, as shown in Figure 6.

Table 3: Energy, Grid and Management Fees

Point of Delivery	Energy Fee [€/kWh]	Grid Fee [€/kW/Month]	Management Fee [€/POD/Month]
Medium Voltage ($P \leq 100$)	UNP	2.65	36.41
Medium Voltage ($100 < P \leq 500$)	UNP	2.38	32.77
Medium Voltage ($P > 500$)	UNP	2.09	31.66

Figure 6: Average daily combined demand of the charging station and a BSS

In Figure 6 it is evident that aggregate demand peaks in the afternoon, while nighttime demand remains minimal due to the absence of swaps and a limited number of charging orders. This pattern presents an opportunity to store energy overnight, thereby alleviating demand during afternoon and evening peak hours when grid demand is typically high. By utilizing energy storage systems to shift demand, cost savings can be achieved, as energy prices are generally lower during nighttime hours. Additionally, the pronounced price fluctuations present an opportunity to efficiently manage photovoltaic (PV) energy production, which can either be delivered directly to the load or injected into the grid.

Figure 7: Load shifting optimization

Figure 7 illustrates the outcomes of load-shifting optimization simulations. These simulations demonstrate a significant shift in energy demand to nighttime, aligning with lower energy prices and a reduction in power absorption during peak hours. The optimization algorithm leverages low-price periods to charge the battery more aggressively, thus maximizing cost efficiency.

Figure 8: Load shifting optimization and PV energy production

Figure 8 compares the original and shifted power demand alongside photovoltaic energy production. The results show how the algorithm effectively optimizes renewable energy utilization by allocating a portion to meet the load requirements and injecting the surplus into the grid. This approach maximizes overall revenues from PV energy production. Finally, analysing the total energy cost reveals a substantial saving of €71,450.16, representing a 45% reduction compared to the initial energy cost of €160,152.92. These findings highlight the significant economic and operational benefits of implementing energy storage and load-shifting strategies.

CONCLUSIONS

The integration of a Battery Swapping Station (BSS) with a photovoltaic power plant presents a significant opportunity to enhance the efficiency and sustainability of electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure. In this study, a mixed-integer linear programming algorithm is proposed to optimize BSS operations, accounting for hourly energy prices and grid constraints. Simulation results demonstrate substantial economic savings and operational improvements, emphasizing the algorithm's ability to leverage cost differentials in electricity pricing. By strategically scheduling battery charging and utilizing renewable energy, the BSS reduces operational costs and maximizes efficiency. A practical case study of a Charging Point Operator (CPO) in northern Italy showcases the real-world application of this optimization model. The integration of a BSS with an existing charging station and a photovoltaic power plant not only balances power loads but also minimizes peak capacity requirements. Load-shifting simulations indicate a significant shift in energy demand to nighttime, aligning with lower energy prices and optimizing renewable energy production for both immediate use and grid injection. This dual approach of demand management and renewable energy utilization highlights the economic and environmental benefits of such integrated systems.

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